

Studies on crystallographic and electrical behavior of neodymium substituted perovskite : $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$

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Abstract : Perovskite structured ceramic phases, namely, $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Nd}_{0.1}\text{MnO}_3$ (LMNd-1) and $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Nd}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ (LMNd-3) synthesized by oxide route method crystallize in the rhombohedral symmetry (space group $R-3c$). Their structure refinement converged to satisfactory values of Rietveld parameters : R_p , R_{wp} and goodness of fit. Infrared absorptions of M-O stretching and bending vibrations have been assigned. Crystal morphology and composition of phases have been analyzed by scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray analysis respectively. Electrical properties of material have been investigated by impedance spectroscopy in the frequency range 42 Hz to 5 MHz at temperatures between 50–300 °C. Nyquist plots show the dominance of grain contribution and Debye-like relaxation in the materials. Conductivity data as a function of temperature and frequency suggest semiconducting behavior of the materials.

Keywords : Crystal structure, powder X-ray diffraction, microstructure, electrical properties.

Introduction

The RMnO_3 (R = rare earth elements) perovskite materials have many applications such as high temperature ceramic superconductors, catalysts, sensors, oxygen gas separation membranes and novel electronic materials¹⁻⁴. The system offers sufficient degree of chemical flexibility which permits the study of relationship between the oxide structure and electronic and magnetic properties in a systematic way. The rare earth substituted lanthanum manganites also have been identified as cathode material for solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) that operate in high temperature range⁵⁻⁸. SOFCs have been studied extensively for a broad spectrum of electrical power generation applications because of their clean and efficient electrical energy production. Their potential for such fuel cells is immense and they promise to be an important alternative energy source for a less oil dependant future^{9,10}. Crystallographic stability, adequate electrical conductivity levels and compatible coefficients of thermal expansion are mandatory for such applications.

The solid state reactivity of perovskite-type oxides basically depends on the nature of A and B ions and their valence states. By replacing part of A or B ions with A' and B' respectively, it is possible to create or suppress

oxygen vacancies on the catalysts. It is well known that the A site doping can change structural, electronic and magnetic properties of perovskite manganite which depend crucially on the doping level as well as the nature of the doping element¹¹⁻¹³. Perovskite structured lanthanum manganite of formula $\text{LaMnO}_{3\pm\delta}$ is an appropriate host lattice for rare earth, alkaline and alkaline earth cation(s) to produce new properties of the materials. Relevant literature reveals that the substitution of La or Mn by another ion directly modifies the chemical and physical properties because of new interactions in the La-O and M-O networks. In particular, rare earth manganite perovskite are being widely studied in recent years due to their magneto-resistance and electrical properties¹⁴. In order to study the structure-property relationship of neodymium doped LaMnO_3 perovskite, crystal structures of neodymium substituted phases have been refined and their electrical behavior investigated in detail.

Experimental

Ceramic route synthesis of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ phases :

Calculated quantities of AR grade $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Nd_2O_3 and MnCO_3 for the stoichiometry $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ (where $x = 0.1$ and 0.3) were thoroughly mixed with

about 10 ml of 1,2,3 propane tri-ol to form a semisolid paste which was then gradually heated initially at 600 °C for 4 h in a crucible. The mixture was reground to micron size, pressed into pellets and sintered in a platinum crucible at 1200 °C for 12 h. The process was repeated to get a polycrystalline solid solution.

Characterization :

The powder X-ray diffraction pattern has been recorded between $2\theta = 10\text{--}120^\circ$ on a Pan Analytical diffractometer (XPRT-PRO) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at step size of $2\theta = 0.017^\circ$ and a fixed counting time of 5 s/step. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) has been carried out on a Zeiss electron microscope system equipped with facility for energy dispersive X-ray analysis. Electrical behaviour of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ (where $x = 0.1$ and 0.3) have been investigated by a.c. impedance method on computer interfaced HIOKI LCR HITESTER 3532-50 impedance analyzer between the frequency range from 42 Hz to 5 MHz. Impedance, capacitance and conductivity data were collected as a function of frequency in the range of ambient temperature to 300 °C over heating and cooling cycles. The sintered pellet's flat surfaces were painted with high purity conducting silver paste followed by drying at 300 °C. After electroding the sample in the form of circular disc (1.29 cm diameter and 0.30 cm thickness), it was placed along with sample holder in the computer interfaced dry well type furnace for electrical measurements.

Results and discussion

Rietveld refinement and crystallographic data :

The powder XRD data show that neodymium substituted lanthanum manganite phase of compositions $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.1$ and 0.3) are iso-structural to LaMnO_3 ^{15,16} which crystallizes in the rhombohedral system (space group $R\bar{3}c$). The conditions for the rhombohedral lattice ($-h+k+l = 3n$, when $h = 0, l = 2n$ and $k = 0, l = 2n$) have been verified for all reflections between $2\theta = 10\text{--}100^\circ$. The structure of the synthetic phases has been refined by Rietveld method¹⁷ using GSAS¹⁸ software, which allows determination of crystal structure, refinement of atomic coordinates, site occupancies and atomic displacement parameters as well as profile parameters (lattice constants, peak shape, peak height, instrument parameters, background). The structure refinement leads to rather good fit between the experimental and calculated XRD pattern (Figs. 1a and 1b) and yields acceptable reliability factors : RF^2 , R_p and R_{wp} (Table 1). The normal probability plot for the histogram gives nearly a linear relationship indicating that the I_0 and I_c values for the most part are normally distributed. The substitution of La^{3+} by the Nd^{3+} ion results in slight alternation of the lattice parameters and unit cell volume of the matrix which shows that the network modifies its dimensions to accommodate the incoming cation without breaking bonds. The final atomic coordinates and isotropic thermal parameters (Table 2), inter-atomic distances and

Fig. 1. Rietveld refinement plots for (a) LMNd-1 and (b) LMNd-3 ceramic samples showing observed (+), calculated (continuous line) and difference (lower) curves. The vertical bars denote Bragg reflections of the crystalline phases.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ceramic phases at room temperature

Structure : Rhombohedral; Space group; $R\text{-}3c$; $Z = 6$		
Parameters	x=0.1	x=0.3
Lattice constants		
$a = b$	5.50209(16)Å	5.48655(16)
c	13.4230(7)	13.4823(7)
$\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ, \gamma = 120^\circ$		
R_p	0.1137	0.1158
R_{wp}	0.1518	0.1536
R_{expected}	0.1095	0.1095
RF^2	0.12622	0.10888
Volume of unit cell	351.912(14)	351.474(13)
S (GoF)	1.39	1.41
Unit cell formula weight	1454.246	1480.668
Density $_{X\text{-ray}}$	6.862	7.022
Slope	1.2959	1.2366

$$R_p = \frac{\sum y_i(\text{obs}) - y_i(\text{cal})}{\sum y_i(\text{obs})}, R_{wp} = \left\{ \frac{\sum w_i (y_i(\text{obs}) - y_i(\text{cal}))^2}{\sum w_i (y_i(\text{obs}))^2} \right\}^2$$

$$R_e = \left[(N-P) / \sum w_i y_{oi}^2 \right]^{1/2}, S = R_{wp} / R_{\text{exp}}$$

$y_{i(o)}$ and $y_{i(c)}$ are observed and calculated intensities at profile point i , respectively. w_i is a weight for each step i . N is the no. of parameters refined.

Table 2. Refined atomic coordinates of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ polycrystalline solid solutions at room temperature

Parameters	x=0.1	x=0.3
La/Nd ($x = 0.0, y = 0.0, z = 0.25$)	0.01259	0.01044
Uiso		
Mn ($x = 0.0, y = 0.0, z = 0.0$)	0.00142	0.00141
Uiso		
O ($x = 0.495, y = 0.0, z = 0.25$)	0.04125	0.07809
Uiso		

polyhedral distortion index (Table 3) and bond angles and bond angle variance (Table 4) have been reported in this communication. Fig. 2 illustrates the DIAMOND view of three dimensional ball-and-stick structure of the proposed model of the material showing the position and interconnectivity of MnO_6 octahedrons and $\text{LaO}_{12}/\text{NdO}_{12}$ polyhedrons. Slight distortion in $\text{LaO}_{12}/\text{NdO}_{12}$ polyhedron has been noted whereas MnO_6 polyhedron chains remain undistorted. The crystallite size (Fig. 3) of the prepared samples along prominent reflecting planes varies between 16–126 nm as estimated by the Debye-Scherrer method¹⁹.

Table 3. Inter-atomic bond distances (Å) and polyhedral distortion (Δ) in polycrystalline

$\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ceramic phases	x=0.1	x=0.3
Bond-distance		
La/Nd-O	2.77855(8)*3	2.77071(8)*3
La/Nd-O	2.72353(8)*3	2.71584(8)*3
La/Nd-O	2.74379(10)*6	2.74927(10)*6
Mn-O	1.94287(5)*6	1.94205(5)*6
La/Nd-La/Nd	3.88534(10)*6	3.88372(10)*6
La/Nd-Mn	3.35574(17)*2	3.37058(17)*2
La/Nd-Mn	3.36782(9)*6	3.36101(9)*6
Δ (LaO_{12})	14.3×10^{-5}	14.0×10^{-5}

Asterisks represent bond multiplicities.

Table 4. O-M-O bond angles (in deg.) and bond angle variance (δ_n) of polycrystalline

$\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ceramic samples	x=0.1	x=0.3
O-M-O		
Bond angles		
O-La-O	178.8509*3	178.8565*3
O-La-O	120.0*3, 120.4880(26)*3	120.0*3, 120.8030(26)*3
O-La-O	120.4200(13)*6, 119.1601(26)*3	120.2582(13)*6, 119.4836(26)*3
O-La-O	60.2440(13)*6, 60.1848(26)*6	60.4015(13)*6, 59.8655(26)
O-La-O	89.4255*6	89.4283*6
O-Mn-O	90.1598(22)*6	90.1166(23)*6
O-Mn-O	89.8402(22)*6	89.8834(23)*6
O-Mn-O	179.9604*3	180.0, 179.9802*2
δ_n	0.022	0.012
Bond angle variance ($\delta_n = \Sigma[(\theta_i - 90)^2 / (n + 1)]$).		

Impedance analysis :

Electrical properties as a function of composition, temperature and frequency have been studied for LMNd-0, LMNd-1 and LMNd-3 by impedance method which is widely used for investigating the electrical behavior of the materials over a wide range of frequency and temperature. The impedance data has been analyzed by complex plane method, which involves plotting the imaginary part Z'' against the real part Z' . In complex impedance plot, each effect viz. grain, grain boundary or grain electrode effect appears as a semicircle whose centre lies on a line below the real axis. In the present study the temperature dependent impedance spectrum (Nyquist plot) of

Fig. 2. DIAMOND view of crystal structure of samarium substituted lanthanum manganite sample depicting coordination sites of La/Nd and Mn.

Fig. 3. Variation of particle size in $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x=0.1$ and 0.3) ceramic phase along prominent reflections.

$\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.1$ and 0.3) reveals that as the temperature increases, the intercept of the semicircles on Z' axis shift towards lower values of Z' , which shows drastic reduction of resistance due to grain or grain boundary. The intercepts of each semicircular arc with real axis (Z') provide the bulk resistance of the material. Here, the decrease of bulk resistance is more dominant at temperature around 220–300 °C which may be due to ionic conduction that predominates at higher temperature. The presence of single semicircular arc at all temperature indicates that the electrical process in the materials arise due to contribution from the bulk of material²⁰ (Figs. 4a and 4b).

Figs. 5a and 5b depict the variation of real part of impedance (Z') with frequency at different temperatures wherein the magnitude of Z' decreases at higher frequencies with increasing temperature. At higher frequencies the value of Z' merges for all the temperatures of the sample. It is observed from the figures that Z' values decrease with increase of temperature indicating reduction of grains, grains boundaries and electrode interface resistance. This indicates existence of negative temperature coefficient of resistance (NTCR) in the sample. The values remain almost constant up to certain fixed frequency and then they sharply decrease with increasing frequency. The coincidence of the impedance (Z') at higher frequencies for all the temperatures shows a possible release of space charge polarization as a result of reduction in the barrier properties of material with rise in temperatures and frequencies²¹.

Variation of the imaginary part of impedance (Z'') with frequency at different temperatures where shifts in the peaks of Z'' towards higher frequency with increasing temperature is mainly attributed due to change in relaxation in the sample (Figs. 6a and 6b). The asymmetric broadening of the peaks suggests the presence of electrical process of the material with spread of relaxation time (indicated by peak width). The relaxation phenomenon may be possibly due to presence of electron at low temperature and defects at higher temperature. Fig. 7 shows the dependence of relaxation time (τ) with inverse of absolute temperature. The characteristic relaxation time was calculated using the relation $\tau = 1/\omega = 1/2\pi f_{\text{max}}$ where f_{max} is the relaxation frequency. It is observed that the value of relaxation time is found to be decreasing with increase in temperature which indicates semiconductor behavior of the material. The semiconducting nature of the grains in ceramics is believed to be due to the loss of oxygen during high temperature sintering process. The activation energy calculated from the slope of $\ln \tau$ versus $10^3/T$ plot was found to be 1.08 and 0.82 eV for LMNd-1 and LMNd-3 respectively. Temperature dependence of bulk resistance has been described in Fig. 8. It is clear that the bulk resistance decreases sharply with rise in temperature up to temperature 220 °C and then decreases slowly. The different rate of increase of bulk conductivity corresponds to different activation energies involved in the different temperature regions.

Fig. 4. Nyquist plot of (a) LMNd-1 and (b) LMNd-3 sample at different temperatures.

Fig. 5. Variation of real part of impedance of (a) LMNd-1 and (b) LMNd-3 ceramic sample with frequency at different temperatures.

Fig. 6. Variation of imaginary part of impedance of (a) LMNd-1 and (b) LMNd-3 sample with frequency at different temperatures.

Variation of a.c. conductivity with frequency at various temperatures can be understood from Figs. 9a and 9b where at lower frequencies plateaus of $\sigma_{a.c.}$ (i.e. frequency independent values of conductivity) corresponds to the d.c. conductivity. The frequency dependent con-

ductivity can be described by the equation $\sigma(\omega) = \sigma_{d.c.} + A\omega^n$, where n is the frequency exponent in the range of $0 < n < 1$, A and n are thermally activated quantities. According to Jonscher²², the origin of the frequency dependence of conductivity lies in the relaxation phenom-

Fig. 7. Variation of relaxation time ($\log \tau$) with inverse of temperature for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ sample.

Fig. 8. Plot of bulk resistance as a function of temperature for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ sample.

Fig. 9. Variation of conductivity of (a) LMNd-1 and (b) LMNd-3 sample with frequency at different temperatures.

ena arising due to mobile charge carriers. When mobile charge carriers hop onto a new site from its original po-

sition, it remains in a state of displacement between two potential energy minima, which includes contributions from other mobile defects. After a sufficient time, the defect could relax until the two minima in lattice potential energy coincide with the lattice site. The conductivity as a function of temperature are well fitted to Arrhenius equation for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.0, 0.1$ and 0.3). The bulk conductivity values at 50°C for un-substituted sample are low in the order of $2.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. However, a sharp increase in bulk conductivity is seen on substitution and rise in the temperature. The activation energy for all the samples was obtained by least square fitting of data at different frequencies (Fig. 10).

Microstructure analysis :

The microstructure and compositional distribution of the title phase has been examined by SEM and EDAX analysis of the specimen. The evolution of LMNd phase can be seen in the scanning electron micrographs of the ceramic sample. The polycrystalline powders are aggregated into flaky agglomerates with grains of size 500–1000 nm (Figs. 11a and 11b). Within the limits of experimental error, the EDAX analytical data on atomic and weight % of La, Nd and Mn are found agreeable with their corresponding expected values. The atomic ratio of $(\text{La}+\text{Nd})/\text{Mn}$ has been found to be 1.20 and 1.12 for $x = 0.1$ and 0.3 respectively. The EDAX spectrum shows that neodymium enters the perovskite matrix (Fig. 11c).

IR analysis :

Absorption bands in FT-IR spectra occurred around

Fig.10. log conductivity as a function of inverse of temperature for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ceramic material.

Fig. 11. Scanning electron microphotograph of (a) LMNd-1, (b) LMNd-3 and (c) EDAX spectrum of polycrystalline $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Nd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ceramic powder.

600 and 400 cm^{-1} . The higher frequency band at 600 cm^{-1} was assigned to the Mn-O stretching vibration (ν_s) mode, which involves the internal motion of a change in Mn-O bond length, the band around 400 cm^{-1} corresponds to the bending (ν_b) mode, which is sensitive to a change in the Mn-O-Mn bond angle. These two bands are related to the environment surrounding the MnO_6 octahedra in the ABO_3 perovskite²³. The presence of an absorption band at 450–500 cm^{-1} could be related to the existence of the La-O stretching²⁴. The bands at 550–670 cm^{-1} are attributed to vibration of Nd-O bond²⁵.

Conclusion

The title ceramic phases synthesized by ceramic route crystallize in rhombohedral symmetry at room temperature. The refinement plots represent a satisfactory structure fit between observed and calculated intensity and *R*-factors. The cell volume and La-O, Mn-O bond distances register a slight decrease with increase of neodymium content. Analysis of impedance spectroscopic data on the material suggests relaxation effects of Debye type. The relaxation frequencies are shifted to higher frequency side with increase in temperature. The complex impedance plots reveal the main contribution of bulk phase in the electrical properties of the material. The variation of bulk a.c. conductivity as a function of temperature demonstrates that the compound exhibits semiconductor behavior.

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